

NATURAL ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH COUNCIL
SCIENTIFIC SERVICES

OPERATIONS REPORT
OF A THEMATIC MULTISPECTRAL
SCANNED SURVEY
OF 36 SELECTED AREAS OF
THE UNITED KINGDOM
IN 3 PARTS
DURING 1985

HUNTING GEOLOGY AND SERVICES LIMITED

ELSTREE WAY, BOREHAMWOOD,
HERTS. WD6 1SB
PROJECT 280 380

TEL NO.: 04752 6161
FAX NO.: 04752 6160
CABLE: HUNTING G

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S U M M A R Y

The Natural Environment Research Council Scientific Services Division on 4th April 1985 commissioned by letter a 3 phase flying and acquisition programme during the Spring-Autumn period of 1985. This contract F3/G6/322 covered 36 individual areas of the United Kingdom where ground research projects by University and N.E.R.C. units were being conducted.

The contract period covered by this report from availability of the Daedalus equipment was limited to a 45 day period over the 3 phases as follows, Phase 1, Spring 15 days: Phase 2, Summer 15 days: Phase 3, Autumn 15 days. At the expiry of the nominated periods, contractual flying and acquisition were terminated, irrespective of whether all areas had been flown.

The aircraft used throughout the flying of the 3 periods was the Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX owned and operated by N.E.R.C. from Kidlington Airport through their handling agents C.S.E. Aviation Limited.

The following sectionalised report describes the field operation and equipment in detail, together with an area by area detail summary of areas flown throughout the three phases of the 1985 flying campaign.

P A R T 1

OPERATIONS REPORT

1. INTRODUCTION

The Thematic Scanner survey described in this report was carried out by Hunting Geology and Geophysics Limited on behalf of the Scientific Services Division of the Natural Environment Research Council (N.E.R.C.) of Swindon, Wiltshire. The 36 areas surveyed and covered by this report are the areas selected by N.E.R.C. to be flown within a maximum period of 45 days as specified in contract document F3/G6/322 of 4th April 1985.

A Piper Navajo/Chieftain aircraft, registration G-BBXX supplied by N.E.R.C. and crewed by C.S.E. Aviation Limited/ Hunting Surveys, fitted with an RC8 survey camera and a Daedalus AADS 1268 thematic scanner commenced flying operations on the 30th April 1985 (Phase 1) and was terminated on the 1st October 1985 (Phase III) with two agreed breaks.

The following report describes the operational aspects of the three periods of flying during this fourth season of N.E.R.C. AADS 1268 surveying in the United Kingdom.

2. INVOLVED PERSONNEL

i N.E.R.C. Superintending Officers

Dr. David F. Williams and Dr. Stuart J. White

ii N.E.R.C. Co-ordinator/Navigator

F.J. Cook

iii C.S.E. Aviation Ltd. Flying Crew

Captain/Pilot	H. John	24 flights
	A Gunter-Smith	21 flights
	R. Payne	1 flight

Aircraft Engineers from C.S.E. pool

iv Hunting Geology & Geophysics Ltd

AADS 1268 Engineers/Operators

	R.E. Westland	38 flights
	D.D. MacDonald	8 flights
Operations Manager	R.D. Williams	

3. FLYING OPERATIONS

3.1 Aircraft and Operational Bases

The survey was flown using the N.E.R.C. Piper Chieftain aircraft registration G-BBXX based at Kidlington (Oxford) Airport. For most of the survey flying, sorties commenced from

the aircraft home base, however night stop/landings were made at Liverpool, Swansea (2) Edinburgh (2) Humberside, Blackpool, Norwich, Prestwick, Dundee (2) East Midlands (2) and Teeside airfields during the three periods of ATM flying.

3.2 Flying Specification and Weather Tolerances

In general the areas to be flown were scattered throughout the United Kingdom and, with the exception of areas in Scotland, the Irish Sea and Bristol Channel, were flown from the aircrafts home base Kidlington. This base gave the flying crews the best possible servicing facilities, weather information and communication with N.E.R.C. at Swindon, as well as space for quick-look processing. The specifications for height, haze, cloud and flight direction were laid down by N.E.R.C. and augmented by their co-ordinator/navigator Mr. F.J.Cook. See Table 1. All day by day flight planning and any special flight permits were arranged by the C.S.E. flight crews in their capacity as aircraft operators. A total of 45 operational days was targeted for the three periods, the finally achieved total of 41.5 days flying are detailed in Table 2 pages 4 and 5.

TABLE 1

ORIGINAL GENERAL CONTRACTUAL FLYING SPECIFICATION

For the sake of continuity the original flight specifications are repeated hereunder. This specification was not conveyed to Huntings for the 1985 flying programme as its interpretation became the express responsibility of the N.E.R.C. co-ordinator/navigator.

1. Cloud

Sites can be flown in cloud free or under a complete cover of cloud. For cloud free up to 5 percent patchy cloud or shadow can be allowed. For patchy cloud the site should not be flown without clearance from the N.E.R.C. project co-ordinator.

Sites should not be flown without prior clearance where the overall luminescence is constantly varying.

2. Precipitation.

No restriction due to recent rain is necessary.

3. Wind.

Whilst calm conditions are preferable the limiting factor is likely to be turbulence effects on the aircraft.

4. Haze/Visibility

In hazy conditions the scanner operator/crew will be responsible for advising on the likely effect and which channels will be affected. The N.E.R.C. project co-ordinator will then decide. In low light conditions the scanner operator must decide if he can record a satisfactory signal by adjusting the gain.

5. Time.

Ideally all flying between 9.30 hours and 16.00 hours. However, if we get clear mornings and/or clear evenings the N.E.R.C. co-ordinator in conjunction with the crew may alter this.

General. If the aircraft flies and the weather closes in, the principal of "flying a target and see" should be adopted, rather than returning empty handed.

Photography. 30 percent forward overlap unless stated otherwise.

Radios

- i) Can the crew transmit on the aircraft radio so that field teams can listen? They should transmit whilst on target and at end.
- ii) The two way radios should be used as needed.
- iii) Radio silence should be observed with the scanner on and the Transponder should be off. These effect the data recording.

Area covered. The scanner should be switched on for the minimum amount of recording to save data processing.

3.3 Navigation

Other than the standard aircraft navigation aids, no specific navigation equipment was added to the N.E.R.C. survey aircraft. However a survey navigator was employed and a wide angle survey camera was supplied and installed, the camera being used on specific scanner lines. Standard forward overlap was maintained throughout the survey period.

ACHIEVED FLIGHT DETAILS

TABLE 2

AREA NO.	NAME	HEIGHT FLOWN (FT)			DIRECTION			GROUND SPEED (KMS)			NO OF RUNS			PHASE FLOWN			DATES FLOWN			CAMERA
		P1	P2	P3	P1	P2	P3	P1	P2	P3	P1	P2	P3	P1	P2	P3	P1	P2	P3	
2	ROTHAMPSTED		2600		NE		150		2		*		31/7/85		Y					
3	LOCH LEVEN	13200			NW		150		1		*		11/5/85		Y					
5	SWANSEA BAY	13000	9650		W	W	170	140	9	5	*	*	8/5/85	27/9/85	Y					
5B	BOSHERTON LAKES	2500/ 1650	6600		SE/ S	NW/ SE	150/ 100	160	6	6	*	*	26/8/85		Y					
6	THE WASH	5000	6600		NW/ SE	NW/ SE	170	160	3	3	*	*	6/5/85	22/9/85	Y					
10	LLANILAE	13000			N/S		170		6		*	*	8/5/85		Y					
11	BALLATER	13000	6500		EW	W	130	120	1	3	*	*	11/5/85	1/10/85	Y					
12	SOUTHAMPTON	2600/ 6000			NE		130		2		*	*	1/5/85		Y					
12/1	MONKS BROOK		2700		N/E		135/ 150		3		*	*	6/8/85 17/8/85		Y					
12/2	CHANDLERS FORD	6600/ 3300	6600		NE	NE/ SW	155/ 170	120	6	3	*	*	3/5/85	17/8/85	Y					
13	NEW FOREST	2600	2700	2600/ 2700	N	N/S SW N	130/ 115	130/ 150	10	8	*	*	1/5/ 10/5/85	6/8/85 17/8/85	Y		24/9/85 1/10/85			
13B	CHESIL BEACH	6600/ 5000			SW/ NW		125		4		*	*	3/8/85		Y					
15	IRISH SEA	13000	5000	13000	E/W	N/S NW/ SE	160	150	6	9	*	*	7/5/85	1/8/85	Y		20/9/85			
1511	RIVER CONWAY	13000			N/S		160		2		*	*	7/5/85		Y					
16	DIDCOT	6600/ 5000			SE/ NW S, SW		170		9		*	*	6/5/85		Y					
17	BLEWBURY	13000			N		175		4		*	*	6/5/85		Y					
18	BAMTRY		2700/ 6600 13000		N/S		110 140		6		*	*	28/9/85		Y					
19	BAMTRY		2700		N/S		110 140 150		5		*	*	26/9/85 28/9/85		Y					
23	TAY ESTUARY		1800/ 2000		S		120		18		*	*	30/9/85		N					
24	BURY ST EDMONDS		11500/ 11700		N/S	N/S	160	130	6	6	*	*	8/8/85	20/9/85 29/9/85	Y					

TABLE 2

AREA NO.	NAME	HEIGHT FLOWN (FT)			DIRECTION			GROUND SPEED (KHS)			NO OF RUNS			PHASE FLOWN			DATES FLOWN			CAMERA
		P1	P2	P3	P1	P2	P3	P1	P2	P3	P1	P2	P3	P1	P2	P3	P1	P2	P3	
25	THEOBALDS PARK		2600		E			150	150	160		5		*		31/7/85			Y	
27	BALLANTRAE	13000			SE/ NE S			150			3		*		11/5/85				Y	
28	M.1		1650		N/S		NE/ NW S	120	120	140	3	3	*	*		25/8/85		22/9/85 26/9/85 28/9/85 29/9/85	Y	
29	FURZE BROOK	6600	3300/ 6600		N		N/S NE	150	120	120	3	9	*	*	3/5/85			25/9/85 27/9/85	Y	
30	BANGOR		6000		S		NE	150	140			2	1	*		17/8/85		27/9/85	Y	
30B	ABER		2700				E		140			1		*				27/9/85	Y	
31	SUTTON BONNINGTON		1650/ 6000/ 3300/ 8000/ 5000/ 10000/ 13000				N		110/ 120/ 140			9		*				26/9/85 28/9/85	Y	
32R	SWINDON	1500 2600			NW			105/ 130			2		*		30/4/85				Y	
CR1.1	PLAS GOGERDDAN		3300		S			110/ 150				1		*		26/8/85			Y	
CR1.2	MORFA MAWR		3300	3500	SW		E	120	110			1	2	*		26/8/85		27/9/85	Y	
CR1.3	BRONYDD MAWR		3000				NE		110			2		*				27/9/85	Y	
CR2	WELLESBOURNE		2650		N			120				1		*				8/8/85 25/8/85	Y	
CR3.1	GLEN SAUGH		13500				N		130			1		*				17/9/85	Y	
CR3.2	SOURHOPE		8000				W		140			1		*				30/9/85	Y	
CR3.3	DUNDEE		13200				N		130			1		*				17/9/85	Y	
CR30	NEW BORO FOREST		5000				NE		150			2		*				27/9/85	Y	

3.4 Survey Diary, Progress and Serviceability

The following is a summary of events throughout the survey period

PHASE 1 APRIL 29TH TO MAY 11TH 1985

April 29th General preparation of equipment.
30th Installation of equipment in aircraft at Kidlington (Oxford) airport plus first productive flight of 1985 campaign, 2 runs over reserve site 32.

May 1st Sortie 2 flown. 11 runs over areas 12 and 13. 3/8ths cloud at 3000 ft
2nd No flying. Poor weather conditions
3rd Sortie 3 flown, 8 runs over areas 29 and 12/2. Poor lamination 2/8ths cloud at 3800 feet plus haze
4th/5th No flying. Poor weather conditions
6th Sorties 4&5 flown. 19 runs over areas 12/2, 16 and 17. Variable cloud amounts from 1/8th to 3/8th at 5000 feet.
7th Sorties 6&7 flown with landings at Liverpool. 9 runs over area 15. Apart from some haze, weather otherwise good.
8th Sorties 8&9 flown with a landing at Swansea. 15 runs over areas 5 and 10. Weather good.
9th No flying. Poor weather conditions
10th Sortie 10 flown. 4 runs over area 13/1. Dull conditions with slight haze. 8/8th cloud cover at 3200 feet.
11th Sortie 11 flown with landings at Edinburgh and Humberside. 7 runs over areas 11, 3 and 27. Weather conditions, clear with 3/8th cloud at 4000 feet initially and increasing, leading to the abandonment of a second sortie in the Bawtry area.

Giving a total on site days for Phase 1 acquisition of 11 days.

PHASE II JULY 31ST TO AUGUST 27TH 1985

July 31st Installation of equipment in aircraft at Kidlington (Oxford) airport plus first sortie of summer campaign. 5 runs over areas 2 and 25. Slight haze with generally 4/8th cloud at 3500 feet.
August 1st Sortie 2 flown. 9 runs over area 15. 6/8 cloud at 5500 feet but more persistent to north of area thereby affecting the length of runs 7 to 9 inclusive.
2nd No flying. Poor weather conditions.
3rd Sortie 3 flown. 4 runs over area 13B. Clear, bright weather with 1/8th to 3/8th cloud at 5000 feet.

4th and 5th No flying. Poor weather conditions.
6th Sortie 4 flown. 3 runs only over areas 12 and 13. Haze and turbulence with variable cloud 1/8th to 3/8th at 3000 feet giving ground cloud shadow over area 13.

7th No flying. Poor weather conditions.
8th Sorties 5,6 and 7 flown with a landing at Norwich. 12 runs flown over areas 24,C2,25. Clear air conditions with 1/8th to 3/8th cloud at 3500 feet.

9th No flying. Poor weather conditions.
10th An attempt to fly area 17 made but aborted due poor weather-cloud. No recordings produced.

11th to 16th No flying. Poor weather conditions.
17th Sorties 8 and 9 flown. 18 runs over areas 12,30 and 13. Clear, smooth conditions with 1/8th to 2/8th cloud at 2500 feet. On completion of flying area 30 the aircraft transitted to Scotland, landing at Prestwick on return flight after poor conditions experienced over Ballantrae area.

25th Sortie 10 flown. 10 runs over areas 6,28 and CR2. Clear, fairly bright conditions with 1/8th to 3/8th cloud building at 3000 feet.

26th Sorties 11 and 12 flown. 11 runs flown over areas 5B and CR1. Fairly bright, smooth conditions with variable cloud 2/8th to 7/8th persisting at 3500 feet. A landing was made at Swansea airport at 11.00 hours.

27th Poor weather conditions no flying. Crew stood down at 15.30 hours and equipment removed at 17.00 hours.

Giving a total on site days for Phase II Acquisition of 14.5 days and 13 days standby.

During the period between phase II and III the aircraft underwent a service period and latterly flew photo cover over nominated river estuaries.

PHASE III SEPTEMBER 13TH TO 1ST OCTOBER 1985

September 13th Installation of ATM equipment in aircraft at Kidlington (Oxford) airport. An attempted sortie over area 29 was aborted at 15.30 hours due poor weather conditions.

14th No flying. Poor weather conditions.
15th An attempted sortie was aborted after 1 hour 25 minutes flying due poor weather conditions.

17th Sorties 1 and 2 flown with a landing at Dundee. 2 runs over area CR3 followed by a transit back to Kidlington. Bright clear conditions, 1/8th cloud at 5000 feet.

18th and 19th No flying. Poor weather conditions.

20th	Sorties 3 and 4 flown. 17 runs over areas 15 and 24. Generally dull/clear conditions with 7/8th cloud at 18,000 feet.
21st	No flying. Poor weather conditions.
22nd	Sortie 5 flown. 1 run over area 28. Bright clear conditions with 2/8th cloud at 3500 feet.
25th	Sortie 7 flown. 6 runs over area 29. Slight haze 4/8th cloud at 5000 feet.
26th	Sortie 8 flown. 5 runs over areas 19,28 and 31. Fairly bright with haze and 3/8th cloud at 3000 feet.
27th	Sorties 9 and 10 flown with a landing at Swansea. 17 runs over areas 29,5,CR1,CR30 and 30B. Bright, hazy conditions with zero cloud.
28th	Sorties 11 and 12 flown with a landing at East Midlands airport. 21 runs over areas 31,18,19,28 and 6. Bright, smooth but very hazy conditions with zero cloud.
29th	Sortie 13 flown. 4 runs over areas 24 and 28. Bright sunshine zero cloud generally with some haze over 28.
30th	Sorties 14,15,16 and 17 flown with landings at Dundee and Edinburgh airports. 19 runs over areas CR3, and 23. Generally dull with slight haze, becoming very turbulent, 3/8th cloud at 4000 feet.
October 1st	Sorties 18 and 19 flown with landings at Edinburgh and Teeside after a night stop Dundee. 10 runs over areas 11 and 13. Generally dull conditions with slight haze and 3/8 cloud at 4000 feet.

Giving a total on site days for Phase III acquisition of 16 days

The weather conditions experienced during the 3 periods of the 1985 campaign were probably the worst since N.E.R.C. commenced their campaigns in 1982. Delayed starts, days completely washed out coupled to weather deterioration after promising starts made Phase II a most disappointing spell. The "standby day" arrangement enabled some areas otherwise lost during the contractual period, to be flown. In all 11.5 days of attempted acquisition have been recorded with 13 days of standby.

4. EQUIPMENT

4.1 Survey Camera

The camera used for this years N.E.R.C. campaign was a Wild RC8 wide angle survey camera using a 15 uag 396 lens and Kodak XX black/white film. This unit was manually operated throughout the survey period by the survey navigator who adjusted the forward overlap to suit the area being flown. The camera was installed in the existing forward camera hole of the N.E.R.C.

aircraft and produced throughout 9X9 format black/white images. The unit had a 6 inch focal length.

The film processing of selected runs was carried out in the photo laboratories of Hunting Survey Ltd, Borehamwood, who over the full season of flying produced a total of 1,404 prints. 540 prints Phase I 271 prints Phase II. 593 prints Phase III. The scale of these prints varied with the differing flying heights of each area. The scale of individual areas together with their "given" names are noted on the photo title strips. Photo cover was not flown over every ATM area and not all the acquired negatives were commissioned for prints. A copy of the photo flight logs and index maps of lines flown has been supplied with the survey prints.

4.2 The Airborne Thematic Mapper

The equipment chosen for the 1985 N.E.R.C contract was again the Daedalus Enterprises Inc. AADS 1268 ATM 11 channel scanner.

This complete sensor unit comprises: A scan head, a spectrometer and a digitiser, coupled in, on this survey, to a AADS 1840 HDDT to b/w film conversion unit, an HDDT playback unit and a Sangamo Sabre 80 III tape recorder, model 3630 1" machine. This combination of units enabled onsite production of HDDTs and 5" wide b/w quick-look prints of any one selected channel of data at aircraft base. Scan speeds were selected to suit the areas being flown and were selected from speeds 12.5, 25 and 50 scan/second available on the equipment as a standard. The S bend correction, another equipment standard, was selected and automatically applied over all areas flown. The standard operating wavelengths and performance parameters for the AADS 1268 ATM scanner are as follows:

TABLE 3

PRIMARY CHANNEL BAND CHANNEL	CHANNEL EDGES IN μ M	12.5 SCANS/SEC NER 1	25 SCANS/SEC NER 1	50 SCANS/SEC NER 1
1	0.42 - 0.45	0.28	0.36	0.52
2	*0.45 - 0.52	0.06	0.07	0.10
3	*0.52 - 0.60	0.05	0.05	0.05
4	0.605- 0.625	0.10	0.10	0.11
5	*0.63 - 0.69	0.05	0.05	0.05
6	0.695- 0.75	0.05	0.05	0.05
7	*0.76 - 0.90	0.03	0.03	0.03
8	0.91 - 1.05	0.01	0.11	0.15
9	*1.55 - 1.75	0.07	0.10	0.17
10	*2.08 - 2.35	0.005	0.006	0.009
11	*8.5 -14.0	0.05	0.07	0.08

* Thematic Mapper bands (except thermal band) broadened for aircraft operations.

i. Noise equivalent radiance in $W \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1}$.

- ii Instantaneous field of view (IFOV) 2.5 MRAD (with 1.25 MRAD option).
- iii Digitised field of view 85.92 deg. (2.5 mr IFOV)
It should be noted that this field of view reduces to 72 degrees when the S bend correction is applied, as throughout this survey.
- iv Velocity/height ratio 0.031 radians/sec - 12.5 scan/sec
(based on 2.5 mr IFOV) 0.062 " " 25.0 " "
0.125 " " 50.0 " "
- v Roll correction +/- 15 degrees
- vi Infrared reference source
2 controllable thermal black bodies with a temperature range of -15 deg. to + 50 degrees C with respect to scan head heat sink temperatures.

Figure 1 outlines in diagrammatic form the functional operations of both scanner head and the spectrometer.

4.3 Radio Communication Units

8. SMC 317L6 3 watt 6 channel 2-way units were supplied to N.E.R.C. to assist in air/ground movements during over flights of selected areas. The radios were tuned to the Hunting licenced frequency of 169.275 Mhz. This licence having previously been allocated to the Hunting Group by the Home Office.

5. DATA ACQUIRED AND PRESENTED

5.1 On site

- a. 19 HDDTs (High Density Data Tapes) and one channel of b/w prints of "quick look" imagery were produced progressively throughout the three survey periods. The HDDT useage was carried forward sortie to sortie until total capacity had been achieved. There was no carry forward of HDDTs from one period to the next e.g Spring to Summer.
- b. 9 x 9 photo cover was taken on all lines flown except area 23 (Tay estuary) when 12 ATM lines without camera were flown. In total 1404 b/w prints plus 302 dupe film positives were produced from the N.E.R.C selected areas throughout the 3 periods. Period by period this amounted to: Period I Spring 593 prints. Period II

AADS1268 DIGITAL MSS SYSTEM - SCAN HEAD / SPECTROMETER - OPTICAL DIAGRAM

Summer 271 prints plus 225 dupe film positives Period III Autumn 540 prints plus 77 dupe film positives. The dupe film positives were only produced for area 15 the Irish Sea.

5.2 Final presentations

- a. The field produced HDDTs were converted to CCTs in the Hunting laboratories at Elstree on their HP.3000 computer where all channels of data per line flown were recompiled with start and scans correlated. No flight line was split onto a second tape. The data is presented on the CCTs in the Hunting's band interleaved raw data format (see description in Table 4)
- b. Parts of entire areas of photo cover taken during the ATM flying were selected by N.E.R.C. or their representative F.J.Cook and presented as either 9x9 B/W prints or dupe film positives in frame form. An index plot of all lines flown with photo cover, showing print and run number on 1:50,000 scale ordnance survey map sheets have also been presented.
- c. A report of operations in 5 copies.

5.3 CCT Format

TABLE 4

HUNTINGS BAND INTERLEAVED ATM RAW DATA TAPE FORMAT

As revision 1.1 of April 1985

1. Daedalus AADS 1268

The Daedalus AADS 1268 is an 11-channel digital airborne scanner recording in the 0.42 to 14.00 μm region of the electromagnetic spectrum.

The wavelengths of each of the 11-channels are shown in Table 3.

The scanner also records a 12th channel which has the same wavelength as channel 11 but with a gain setting of a half of that of channel 11. This channel can be of particular use when data in channel 11 is saturated.

2. Tape Format

Data is recorded on a computer industry standard 0.5 inch nine track magnetic tape with a packing density of 1600 bits per inch (bpi).

3. Recorded Data Format

The data is recorded on the tape in standard band interleaved by line (BIL) format.

The following paragraphs describe how the data is physically organised on the tape.

3.1 Header Record

This record is 576 bytes long and contains ASCII informative data. This record is split into 22 sub-records as described in Table A. Each sub-record is terminated with a carriage return and linefeed.

T A B L E A

Line No.	Length (bytes)	Bytes Nos.	Contents
1	40	1-40	Hunting Geology and Geophysics AADS 1268
2	52	41-92	Clients name
3	13	93-105	Tape nnn
4	23	106-128	Flight Date dd- <u>mmm</u> -yy
5	12	129-140	Flight nn
6	34	141-174	Bands n.m.o.p.....
7	39	175-213	Site - erehwon
8	35	214-248	Scan/Frame Count - Start nnnnnn
9	36	249-284	Scan/Frame Count - Finish <u>mmmmmm</u>
10	30	285-314	Ground Clearance nnnn metres
11	25	315-339	Ground Speed nnnn Knots
12	22	340-361	Pixel nn metres wide
13	22	362-383	Pixel mm metres long
14	17	384-400	750 Frame Bytes
15	25	401-425	Record Size nnnnn Bytes
16	24	426-449	Band Frame Interleaved
17	21	450-470	Video Start Byte 24

18	20	471-490	Video End Byte 739
19	13	491-503	BB1 Byte 23
20	14	504-517	BB2 Byte 740
21	29	518-546	n.nn Milliradian Resolution
22	30	547-576	Source HDDT nnn

3.2 Tape Data Record

These records will be of constant size within tape files. That size will depend on the number of channels of data contained in the file.

Table B itemises all the possible data record sizes.

T A B L E B

No.Bands	Block Size(bytes)
1	7500
2	7500
3	9000
4	9000
5	7500
6	9000
7	10500
8	6000
9	6750
10	7500
11	8250
12	9000

The layout of these bytes is shown in Table C.

T A B L E C

Byte No.	Content
1-750	Scan line 1 Channel 1
751-1500	Scan line 1 Channel 2
1501-2250	Scan line 1 Channel 3
etc.	etc.

3.3 Logical Data Record

Logical data records are of a constant size of 750 bytes. They contain the data for one scan line for one channel.

The contents of these 750 bytes are shown in Table D.

T A B L E D

Byte No.	Recording Type	Description
1-4	binary	Start of frame code
5	binary BCD	Run number (4 msb) Extended line count (4 lsb)
6-8	BCD	Line count
9-12	BCD	Thumbwheel setting
13-14	BCD	Calibration source 1
15-16	BCD	Calibration source 2
17-21	binary	External digital data
22	binary	Gain, S bend and channel number
23	binary	Digitised BB1
24-739	binary	Video data
740	binary	Digitised BB2
741-750	binary	End of frame code

3.3.1 Start of Frame Code

This is a 4 byte binary pattern used to synchronise the scan. The contents of the 4 bytes are shown in Table E.

T A B L E E

Byte No.	Contents
1	01010110
2	10100101
3	10100110
4	10101111

3.3.2 Run Number/Extended Line Count

This is a single byte. The 4 most significant bits contain the sortie number in binary. The 4 least significant bits contain the millions digit of the scan line number recorded in binary coded decimal.

3.3.3 Line Count

This is a 3 byte representation of the scan line number which is recorded in binary coded decimal.

3.3.4 Thumbwheel Setting

This is a 4 byte representation of the contents of the thumbwheel of the scanner itself. It is recorded in binary coded decimal.

3.3.5 Calibration Source

These two pairs of bytes contain the temperatures (degrees Celcius) of the scanners two black body references. They are recorded in binary coded decimal as shown in Table F.

T A B L E F

Bit No.	Content
15	Sign bit 0 = negative 1 = positive
14-12	Tens of degrees
11-8	Degrees
7-4	Tenths of degree
0-3	Hundreths of degree

3.3.6 External Digital Data

These 5 bytes contain certain operational parameters for the scanner. The only parameter of any relevance is contained in the two most significant bits of byte 17. These contain the speed at which the scanner is working. See Table G for options.

T A B L E G

Contents of 2 msb byte 17	Meaning
00	12.5 scans/sec
01	25 scans/sec
10	50 scans/sec

3.3.7 Gain, S Bend, Channel Number

These are all contained in a single byte.

The gain and S bend are encoded in the four most significant bits of the byte as shown in Table H.

The channel number is encoded in the four least significant bits of the byte as shown in Table J.

T A B L E H

Contents of 4 msb	Gain Setting	S Bend Setting
0101	8	Out
0100	4	Out
0011	2	Out
0010	1	Out
0001	0.5	Out
1101	8	In
1100	4	In
1011	2	In
1010	1	In
1001	0.5	In

T A B L E J

Contents of 4 lsb	Channel No.
0001	1
0010	2
0011	3
0100	4
0101	5
0110	6
0111	7
1000	8
1001	9
1010	10
1011	11
1100	12

3.3.8 Digitised BB1

This is a single byte which contains the binary representation of the intensity recorded when the scanner was viewing black body reference 1.

This is recorded as if the scanner was set with a gain of 1 for channel 11.

3.3.9 Video Data

These are contained in 716 consecutive bytes and contain the data for 716 pixels across the scan line.

3.3.10 Digitised BB2

This is a single byte which contains the binary representation of the intensity recorded when the scanner was viewing black body reference 2.

This is recorded as if the scanner was set with a gain of 1 for channel 11.

3.3.11 End of Frame Code

These are contained in ten consecutive bytes which contain a binary in pattern used to synchronise the scan. The contents of each of the 10 bytes is 10101010.

4. Common Conventions

4.1 Byte Numbering

The data is packed two bytes per 16 bit computer word. These are numbered in the standard Hewlett Packard form such that the most significant byte is numbered 1 and the least significant 2.

This standard is different from that used by Digital and other computer manufacturers who number them the other way round.

4.2 Bit Numbering

The bits within a 16 bit computer word are numbered 0 to 15 with 0 being the least significant bit.

5. Conclusions

5.1 Input to Image Processing Systems

This data is blocked to gain maximum data content on to CCT which means that it is not readily input to an image processing system.

Input is usually achieved by special software or by deblocking the data.

5.2 Non Hewlett Packard Computers

If this data is to be read on to a non Hewlett Packard computer it may be necessary to swap the bytes within each 16 bit word.

If this is not done the resulting image will look grainy. This shows itself up on straight line features which go diagonally across the image. They will look very stepy.

5.4

TABLE 5

EXAMPLE OF TAPE RELATED INPUT DATA

TAPE 1 or 2 or 3 etc.

Site - New Forest 13

N.E.R.C.

Flight Date 26-May-85

Bands 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10-11-12

Scan/Frame Count - Start 23000 Scan/Frame Count - Finish 26999

Scan Speed = 12.5 Scans Per Second

Low Blackbody = 17 Low Temp Ref = 14.78 Degrees Celcius

High Blackbody = 252 High Temp Ref = 44.71 Degrees Celcius

Gains=4.0 2.0 2.0 4.0 2.0 4.0 2.0 4.0 2.0 2.0 1.0 0.0

6. MATERIALS SUPPLIED TO CLIENT

6.1 Survey Film

A total of 1404 9"x9" black/white survey photographs plus 302 dupe film positives of varying scales and all negative film produced over the clients selected areas have been supplied to Swindon.

6.2 "Quick Look" Imagery

Uncorrected 5" wide b/w prints of one channel of data along all lines flown were produced with the field equipment and presented to the client for inspection.

6.3 CCTs

An overall total of 264 master CCTs covering all selected areas flown have been supplied, plus a duplicate set as contractually required.

6.4 HDDTs

The field produced HDDTs covering all areas flown are held by Huntings pending a directive as to their disposal within the next 12 months. Total held for 1985 campaign 18.

6.5 Flight Maps

A full set of 1:50,000 scale ordnance survey map sheets covering each area flown, with recovered flight tracks plotted from 9"x9" survey prints superimposed, have been supplied with each periods flying. Duplicate maps have been supplied if area flown again in seperate periods.

6.6 Operations Report

An operations report covering the full 1985 campaign and complete with data tape formats in 5 copies has been presented.

P A R T 2

FIGURES

FIGURE 2

AREA NO. 2

FIGURE 3

AREA No. 3

NSS '85 LOCH LEVEN
 AREA OF INTEREST

FLIGHT LINE →
 SWATH - - - - (10m PIXELS)

FIGURE 4

AREA NO. 5

View A. (at Lat. 52°08' N., Long. 6°36' W.)

FIGURE 5

AREA NO. 5B

FIGURE 6

AREA NO. 6

Study area for which
aerial photography is requested
at between 1:10,000 and 1:15,000
(stereo cover, B&W PAN sufficient)

Representative portion
of study area for which aircraft
scanner data is requested.
(O.S. 1:250,000 sheet 5
Eastern Highlands)

FIGURE 8
AREA NO. 11

FIGURE 9

AREA NO. 12

Rownhams

Lord's Wood

Aldermoor

Holy Trinity Church

FIGURE 10

AREA NO. 12/1^{wn}

Ringwood
 21 km or 13 miles
 A31

Southampton
 11 km or 7 miles
 A36

SOUTHAMPTON

Southampton
 6 km or 4 miles
 A305

FIGURE 11

AREA NO. 12/2

MSS

2

42 43 44 EASTLEIGH 45 46 47

H A M P S H I R E

1000 2000 3000 4000 5000 6000

FIGURE 12

AREA NO. 13

MSS-85 E. J. MILTON
 UNIV. SOUTHAMPTON 0703/559122
 * 2219/2215
 UPDATED FLIGHT LINES 22/4/85
 NEW FOREST: DENNY LODGE

Flying height: 800M, N-S
 Normal Ground Resolution: 2M
 Overlap required.
 Simultaneous Ground Data Collec.

FIGURE 13

AREA NO. 13B

WEYMOUTH AND PORTLAND DISTRICT

WEYM

PORTLAND HARBOUR

60 61 62 63 64 65 66 67 68 69

ENGLISH CHANNEL

FIGURE 13/1

2

SY

SY

1:49,000

68

69

70

71

72

73

74

75

76

77

78

AREA NO. 1511

I. J. BARNSLEY, BIRKBECK AND UNIVERSITY COLLEGES,

AREA NO. 16

PROPOSED FLIGHT-LINES FOR THE MSS-85 AIRBORNE REMOTE SENSING CAMPAIGN — DIDCOT STUDY AREA.

FIGURE 17

AREA NO. 17

FIGURE 18

AREA NO. 18

AREA NO. 19

BANTRY B

BANTRY A

FIGURE 19
AREA NO. 23

Long Op 35° E

13 km or 8 miles

9 km or 5 miles

7 km or 4 miles

Lat 52° 20' N

FOREST HEATH DISTRICT

10 km or 6 miles

FIGURE 21

AREA NO. 25

BALLANTRAE

FIGURE 23

AREA NO. 28

FIGURE 23/1

FIGURE 24
AREA NO. 29

29

OS
1:50,000
SHEET 115

FIGURE 25
AREA NO. 30

FIGURE 26

AREA NO. 30B

FIGURE 27

AREA NO. 31

LOUGHBOROUGH

SHEPshed

CHARNW

Lat 51°35' N
87 Swindon
5 km or 3 miles
A 420

THAMESDOWN DISTRICT

6 km or 4 miles
A 419

Swindon
8 km or 5 miles

90
89
88
86
85
84
83
82
81
80
79
78
77
76

FIGURE 30

AREA NO. CRL.2.

© Crown Copyright 1966

REVISION INFORMATION
 Fully revised 1964
 except Low Water Mark
 which was plotted from
 photographs dated June 1965
 Major roads revised 1965

PUBLIC RIGHTS OF WAY

SNOWDONIA NATIONAL PARK

Index to adjoining sheets
 Hatching denotes overlaps

Differer

1°47'
1°19'
1°46'
1°18'

al
 decreasing

FIGURE 31

D AREA NO. CR1.3.

1000
32
305

FIGURE 32

AREA NO. CR2.

NATIONAL VEGETABLE RESEARCH STATION
 WELLESBOURNE, WARWICK
 Tel: Wellesbourne 382

①

Sheet 45 Glen Saugh

FIGURE 33

AREA NO. CR3.1.

Sheets 74/80
Sourhope

FIGURE 34
AREA NO. CR3.2.

2

MAIN AREA OF INTEREST

MAIN TARGETS WITHIN AREA

Dog Bank

It larger area possible

A YPC

FIGURE 35/1

(Numbered in priority)
 (Lettered in priority)

2 MAIN AREA OF INTEREST
 B MAIN TARGET WITHIN AREA

FIGURE 36

AREA NO. CR30.

The figures in blue along this side of the map are EASTINGS and must be quoted first when giving a grid reference

25'

20'

SCALE 1:50 000

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

1985 SURVEY

Phase ...².....

Area No. and Name:	2 ROTHAMSTED.	Map Sheet Nos. O/S:	-
Flying Height:	2600	Direction Flown:	NE
Flight Conditions:	Slight haze 4/8 cloud 3500	No. of Lines:	2
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints:	3	No. of Scan Lines:	1800
Film Forward Overlap (%):	60	No. of CCTs:	1
Ground Speed (knots):	150	Scan Speed rps:	50
Time Flown (GMT):	1525-1526 1604-1605.	Tape Footage:	108
Research Team Availability:	1/N/A.	"S" Bend Correction:	YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic
Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter
unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Phase ...¹.....

Area No. and Name:	3 LOCH LEVEN	Map Sheet Nos. O/S:	-
Flying Height:	13200	Direction Flown:	NW
Flight Conditions:	Initially clear 3/8 cloud 4000	No. of Lines:	1
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints:	5	No. of Scan Lines:	1200
Film Forward Overlap (%):	60	No. of CCTs:	1
Ground Speed (knots):	150	Scan Speed rps:	12.5
Time Flown (GMT):	0911-0913	Tape Footage:	58
Research Team Availability:	1/N/A.	"S" Bend Correction:	YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic
Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter
unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

1985 SURVEY

Phase ...1+3...

Area No. and Name:	5 SWANSEA BAY.	Map Sheet Nos. O/S:	-
Flying Height:	9650 13000	Direction Flown:	W
Flight Conditions:	Good, bright, some haze, zero cloud.	No. of Lines:	9/4
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints:	59/42	No. of Scan Lines:	43,100
Film Forward Overlap (%):	60	No. of CCTs:	14
Ground Speed (knots):	170/140	Scan Speed rps:	12.5
Time Flown (GMT):	0903-1002 1102-1105 1224- 1302 1356-1400 1509-1558.	Tape Footage:	2130
Research Team Availability:	1/N/A.	"S" Bend Correction:	YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Phase ...2...

Area No. and Name:	5B BOSHERTON LAKES	Map Sheet Nos. O/S:	-
Flying Height:	1650 2500	Direction Flown:	SE/S
Flight Conditions:	2/8 -7/8 cloud at 3500 otherwise bright/smooth.	No. of Lines:	6
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints:	12	No. of Scan Lines:	11,200
Film Forward Overlap (%):	60	No. of CCTs:	3
Ground Speed (knots):	150/100	Scan Speed rps:	50
Time Flown (GMT):	1025-1038 1216-1222	Tape Footage:	713
Research Team Availability:	1/N/A.	"S" Bend Correction:	YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

1985 SURVEY

Phase .1+2+3.

Area No. and Name:	6 THE WASH.	Map Sheet Nos. O/S:	-
Flying Height:	6600	Direction Flown:	NW/SE
Flight Conditions:	1/8-3/8 cloud at 3000 and building, otherwise clear zero cloud haze.	No. of Lines:	3/3/3.
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints:	63/21/39	No. of Scan Lines:	32,100
Film Forward Overlap (%):	60	No. of CCTs:	10
Ground Speed (knots):	160/110	Scan Speed rps:	25 12.5
Time Flown (GMT):	1713-1733 0946-1002 1605-1623.	Tape Footage:	1792.
Research Team Availability:	1/N/A.	"S" Bend Correction:	YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Phase ...1....

Area No. and Name:	10 LLANILAE	Map Sheet Nos. O/S:	-
Flying Height:	13000	Direction Flown:	N/S
Flight Conditions:	Good.	No. of Lines:	4
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints:	30	No. of Scan Lines:	9,700
Film Forward Overlap (%):	60	No. of CCTs:	6
Ground Speed (knots):	170	Scan Speed rps:	12.5
Time Flown (GMT):	1023-1044 1319-1328	Tape Footage:	534.
Research Team Availability:	1/N/A.	"S" Bend Correction:	YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

1985 SURVEY

Phase ...1+3...

Area No. and Name:	11 BALLATER.	Map Sheet Nos. O/S:	-
Flying Height:	6500 13000	Direction Flown:	E/W
Flight Conditions:	Initially clear. Dull/ Slight haze. 3/8 cloud 4000.	No. of Lines:	3/3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints:	13/28	No. of Scan Lines:	11,300
Film Forward Overlap (%):	60	No. of CCTs:	4
Ground Speed (knots):	130/120	Scan Speed rps:	12.5
Time Flown (GMT):	0841-0844 1000-1021	Tape Footage:	611
Research Team Availability:	1/N/A.	"S" Bend Correction:	YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Phase ...1....

Area No. and Name:	12 SOUTHAMPTON	Map Sheet Nos. O/S:	-
Flying Height:	2600 6000	Direction Flown:	NE
Flight Conditions:	3/8 cloud 3000. Haze, turbulence 1/8-3/8 cloud. 3000.	No. of Lines:	2
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints:	16	No. of Scan Lines:	3900
Film Forward Overlap (%):	60	No. of CCTs:	2
Ground Speed (knots):	130	Scan Speed rps:	50 25
Time Flown (GMT):	0855-0913	Tape Footage:	202
Research Team Availability:	1/N/A.	"S" Bend Correction:	YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

1985 SURVEY

Phase ...2...

Area No. and Name:	12/1 MONKS BROOK.	Map Sheet Nos. O/S:	-
Flying Height:	2700	Direction Flown:	N/NE
Flight Conditions:	1/8 4/8 cloud 3000 bright but hazy	No. of Lines:	3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints:	6	No. of Scan Lines:	4,300
Film Forward Overlap (%):	60	No. of CCTs:	2
Ground Speed (knots):	135/150	Scan Speed rps:	50
Time Flown (GMT):	0937-0942 0922-0923	Tape Footage:	249.
Research Team Availability:	1/N/A.	"S" Bend Correction:	YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Phase ..1+2..

Area No. and Name:	12/2 CHANDLERS FORD.	Map Sheet Nos. O/S:	-
Flying Height:	3300 6600	Direction Flown:	NE/SW
Flight Conditions:	haze poor lumination 2/8 cloud 3800. Variable cloud 1/8 3/8	No. of Lines:	6/3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints:	32/10	No. of Scan Lines:	20,100
Film Forward Overlap (%):	60	No. of CCTs:	7
Ground Speed (knots):	155/170	Scan Speed rps:	50 25 12.5
Time Flown (GMT):	1130-1142 1345-1412 0924-0947.	Tape Footage:	1128
Research Team Availability:	1/N/A.	"S" Bend Correction:	YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

1985 SURVEY

Phase 1+2+3..

Area No. and Name:	13 NEW FOREST.	Map Sheet Nos. O/S:	-
Flying Height:	2600 2700	Direction Flown:	N/S NE/SW
Flight Conditions:	3/8 cloud 3000. Slight haze at 3200. 4/8 cloud 5000 haze/smoke 3/8 cloud 4000 dull.	No. of Lines:	10/10/14
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints:	189/81/151	No. of Scan Lines:	155,800
Film Forward Overlap (%):	60	No. of CCTs:	50
Ground Speed (knots):	130/115 130/150	Scan Speed rps:	50
Time Flown (GMT):	0929-1016 1116-1137	Tape Footage:	6796
Research Team Availability:	0956-0958 0847-0921 1/N/A.	"S" Bend Correction:	YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic
Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter
unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Phase ...²....

Area No. and Name:	13 B CHESIL BEACH.	Map Sheet Nos. O/S:	-
Flying Height:	5000 6600	Direction Flown:	SW/NE
Flight Conditions:	Clear bright	No. of Lines:	4
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints:	1/8-3/8 5000. 30	No. of Scan Lines:	10,400
Film Forward Overlap (%):	60	No. of CCTs:	5
Ground Speed (knots):	125	Scan Speed rps:	25
Time Flown (GMT):	1020-1045	Tape Footage:	507
Research Team Availability:	1/N/A.	"S" Bend Correction:	YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic
Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter
unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

1985 SURVEY

Phase 1+2+3

Area No. and Name: 15 IRISH SEA Map Sheet Nos. O/S: -
 Flying Height: 5000 Direction Flown: E/W N/S
 Flight Conditions: 13000 NW/SE
 No. of 9" x 9" photo prints: 5500, Dull clear with 7/8 cloud at 18000. No. of Lines: 6/9/13
 93/225/77 No. of Scan Lines: 229,500
 Film Forward Overlap (%): 60 No. of CCTs: 49
 Ground Speed (knots): 160/150/140 Scan Speed rps: 25 12.5
 Time Flown (GMT): 1121-1156 1217-1243 Tape Footage: 7552
 0942-1135 1013-1229
 Research Team Availability: 1/N/A. "S" Bend Correction: YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX
 Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens
 Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Phase 1

Area No. and Name: 15ii RIVER CONWAY. Map Sheet Nos. O/S: -
 Flying Height: 13000 Direction Flown: N/S
 Flight Conditions: Zero cloud, bright but some haze. No. of Lines: 2
 No. of 9" x 9" photo prints: - No. of Scan Lines: 6,600
 Film Forward Overlap (%): 60 No. of CCTs: 2
 Ground Speed (knots): 160 Scan Speed rps: 12.5
 Time Flown (GMT): 1248-1301 Tape Footage: 340
 Research Team Availability: 1/N/A. "S" Bend Correction: YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX
 Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens
 Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

1985 SURVEY

Phase 2+3

Area No. and Name: 28
Flying Height: 1650
Direction Flown: N/S
Map Sheet Nos. O/S: -

Flight Conditions: Clear some cloud at 3000. No. of Lines: 3/22
2/8 cloud at 3500 Bright, 3/8 cloud
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints: 47/107
No. of Scan Lines: 48,500

Film Forward Overlap (%): 60
Ground Speed (knots): 120/140
Scan Speed rps: 50
Tape Footage: 1314-1317 1431-1432 1524-1527.

Time Flown (GMT): 0936-1121 0930-0935
Research Team Availability: 1/N/A
"S" Bend Correction: YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX

Camera: Wild RC8, wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner: Daidalus ADS 1268 11 channel Thematic
Scanner with ADS 1840 film converter
unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Phase 1+3

Area No. and Name: 29
Flying Height: 6600
Direction Flown: N/S
Map Sheet Nos. O/S: -

Flight Conditions: Hazy, poor illumination
No. of Lines: 3/9
No. of Scan Lines: 29,200

Film Forward Overlap (%): 60
Ground Speed (knots): 150/120
Scan Speed rps: 25 12.5
Tape Footage: 1039-1107 1532-1553

Time Flown (GMT): 1007-1027
Research Team Availability: 1/N/A
"S" Bend Correction: YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX

Camera: Wild RC8, wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner: Daidalus ADS 1268 11 channel Thematic
Scanner with ADS 1840 film converter
unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

1985 SURVEY

Phase 2+3

Area No. and Name: 30 BANGOR. Map Sheet Nos. O/S: - on data

Flying Height: 2400
 6000

Flight Conditions: 1/8-2/8 cloud at 6000 ft. 2500. Clear. 3/17

No. of 9" x 9" photo prints: 3/17

Film Forward Overlap (%): 60

Ground Speed (knots): 150/140

Time Flown (GMT): 1235-1242 1540-1543.

Research Team Availability: 1/N/A

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Var 396 Lens

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chietain G-BBXX

Map Sheet Nos. O/S: - on data

Direction Flown: NE

No. of Lines: 2

No. of Scan Lines: 12,000

Film Forward Overlap (%): 60

Scan Speed rps: 50.25

Tape Footage: (TMD) 626

Bend correction: YES

Area No. and Name: 30B. ABER. Map Sheet Nos. O/S: - on data

Flying Height: 2700

Flight Conditions: Zero cloud some haze/ bright.

No. of 9" x 9" photo prints: 5

Film Forward Overlap (%): 60

Ground Speed (knots): 140

Time Flown (GMT): 1549-1550.

Research Team Availability: 1/N/A

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Var 396 Lens

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chietain G-BBXX

Map Sheet Nos. O/S: - on data

Direction Flown: E

No. of Lines: 1

No. of Scan Lines: 1600

Film Forward Overlap (%): 60

Scan Speed rps: 50

Tape Footage: (TMD) 83

Bend correction: YES

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

1985 SURVEY

Phase : 3

Area No. and Name:	31	SUTTON BOWNINGTON
Flying Height:	3300	6000-5000
Direction Flown:	N	
No. of Lines:	9	Some haze/bright cloud
No. of Scan Lines:	8300	at 3000. 3/8 Very hazy, bright, zero cloud.
Film Forward Overlap (%):	60	
Ground Speed (knots):	110/120/140	
Scan Speed rps:	50 25 12.5	
Tape Footage:	507	
"S" Bend Correction:	YES	1/N/A.
Research Team Availability:		

Aircraft:

N.E.R.C. Navajo G-BrXX

Camera:

Wild rgb. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner:

Daedalus AFD 1568 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AFD 1840 film converter unit and Sage III tape recorder

Phase : 1

Area No. and Name:	32B	SWINDON
Flying Height:	1500	2600
Direction Flown:	NM	
No. of Lines:	2	Clear bright
No. of Scan Lines:	2400	3/8 cloud 3000.
Film Forward Overlap (%):	60	
Ground Speed (knots):	105/130	
Scan Speed rps:	50	
Tape Footage:	144	
"S" Bend Correction:	YES	1/N/A.
Research Team Availability:		

Aircraft:

N.E.R.C. Navajo G-BrXX

Camera:

Wild rgb. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner:

Daedalus AFD 1568 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AFD 1840 film converter unit and Sage III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

1985 SURVEY

Phase ...

Area No. and Name: CRI.1. PLAS GOEKODAN Map Sheet Nos. O/S: ON SETH

Flying Height: 3300

Direction of Flight: Direction of Flight: S

Flight Conditions: Fairly bright smooth variable cloud 2/8-7/8 at 3500 zero cloud

No. of 9" x 9" photo prints: bright. 13

Film Forward Overlap (%): 60

Ground Speed (knots): 110/150

Scan Speed (ft/ps): 25

Tape Footage: (TMD) 369.

"S" Bend correction: YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chetain G-BBXX .B.A.M

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle lens 396 lens

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel thermal Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name: CRI.2. MORFA MAMR. Map Sheet Nos. O/S: ON SETH

Flying Height: 3300

Direction of Flight: Direction of Flight: SM

Flight Conditions: Fairly bright. 2/8-7/8 cloud at 3500.

No. of 9" x 9" photo prints: 5/4

Film Forward Overlap (%): 60

Ground Speed (knots): 120/110

Scan Speed (ft/ps): 25

Tape Footage: (TMD) 110

"S" Bend correction: YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chetain G-BBXX .B.A.M

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle lens 396 lens

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel thermal Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

1985 SURVEY

Phase 2+3

Area No. and Name: CRL.3. BRONYDD MAWR.
 Flying Height: 3000
 Flight Conditions: Zero cloud Bright
 No. of 9" x 9" photo prints: 8
 No. of Lines: 2
 Direction Flown: NE
 Map Sheet Nos. O/S: -

Area No. and Name: CR2. WELLES BOURNE.
 Flying Height: 2650
 Flight Conditions: Clear. 1/8-3/8
 No. of Lines: 3
 Direction Flown: N
 Map Sheet Nos. O/S: -

Research Team Availability: 1/N/A
 "S" Bend Correction: YES

Time Flown (GMT): 1400-1406.
 Ground Speed (knots): 110
 Scan Speed rps: 25
 Tape Footage: 432

Film Forward Overlap (%): 60
 No. of CTS: 2
 No. of Scan Lines: 2300

Film Forward Overlap (%): 60
 No. of CTS: 2
 No. of Scan Lines: 15,100

Camera: Wild RC8, wide angle 6" 15 Var 396 Lens
 Scanner: DadaPlus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BXKX

Phase 2

Area No. and Name: CR2. WELLES BOURNE.
 Flying Height: 2650
 Flight Conditions: Clear. 1/8-3/8
 No. of Lines: 3
 Direction Flown: N
 Map Sheet Nos. O/S: -

Area No. and Name: CR2. WELLES BOURNE.
 Flying Height: 2650
 Flight Conditions: Clear. 1/8-3/8
 No. of Lines: 3
 Direction Flown: N
 Map Sheet Nos. O/S: -

Research Team Availability: 1/N/A
 "S" Bend Correction: YES

Time Flown (GMT): 1144-1200
 Ground Speed (knots): 120
 Scan Speed rps: 50
 Tape Footage: 922

Film Forward Overlap (%): 60
 No. of CTS: 4
 No. of Scan Lines: 15,100

Film Forward Overlap (%): 60
 No. of CTS: 4
 No. of Scan Lines: 15,100

Camera: Wild RC8, wide angle 6" 15 Var 396 Lens
 Scanner: DadaPlus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BXKX

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

1985 SURVEY

Phase : 3

Area No. and Name: CR3.1. GLEN SAUGH. Map Sheet Nos. O/S: 3, 4, 5
 Flying Height: 13500
 Flight Conditions: Bright/clear with 1/8 cloud at 5000.
 No. of 9" x 9" photo prints: -
 Film Forward Overlap (%): 60
 Ground Speed (knots): 130
 Time Flown (GMT): 1340-1342
 Research Team Availability: 1/N/A.
 "S" Bend correction: YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX
 Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 15 Vag 396 lens
 Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 II channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter
 unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name: CR3.2. SOURHOPE. Map Sheet Nos. O/S: 1, 2, 3
 Flying Height: 8000
 Flight Conditions: 3/8 cloud 4000, dull, slight haze.
 No. of 9" x 9" photo prints: 7.
 Film Forward Overlap (%): 60
 Ground Speed (knots): 140
 Time Flown (GMT): 1253-1255
 Research Team Availability: 1/N/A.
 "S" Bend correction: YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX
 Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 15 Vag 396 lens
 Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 II channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter
 unit and Sabre III tape recorder

